

Low field pediatric brain magnetic resonance Image Segmentation and quality Assurance: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Low field pediatric brain magnetic resonance Image Segmentation and quality Assurance

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

LISA

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

In early life, an accurate description of the structural changes in the developing human brain is crucial for understanding healthy development and identifying neurodevelopmental disorders. Existing adult brain deep learning (DL) based segmentation tools struggle with pediatric MRI due to poor gray/white matter differentiation and rapid growth. These challenges impair the ability of existing algorithms to accurately segment pediatric brain structures even with high-field (1.5T or 3T) MRI systems. In low and middle-income countries, high-field MRI systems are rare due to their high cost and maintenance requirements. To fill this gap, 0.064T Hyperfine SWOOP scanners are being tested in these settings by the UNITY Consortium, funded by the Gates Foundation. Despite lower image quality, low-field MRI offers portability, cost-effectiveness, and eliminates the need for sedation in children. To continue translating recent improvements in infant brain segmentation to underprivileged communities, we resume the Low-field pediatric brain magnetic resonance Image Segmentation and quality Assurance (LISA) challenge.

This year, we will expand the LISA challenge tasks, along with their associated datasets. In the past, Task 1 involved evaluating objective, quantifiable quality assurance (QA) methods that rated the overall quality of low-field MRI to ensure the acquired MRI met specific accuracy and consistency standards. For LISA 2026, we will subdivide this into Task 1a, which will focus again on image artifact evaluation, and Task 1b, which will concentrate on improving image quality through artifact removal or reduction to recover data that would otherwise be substandard. Task 2 has centered around the automatic segmentation of subcortical structures. Previous iterations focused on individual structures, the hippocampi and basal ganglia; however, we are now expanding to a multi-structure segmentation task that encompasses all the deep gray matter structures that can be reliably segmented along with the corpus callosum, and ventricular systems. Specifically, the challenge now includes the hippocampi (critical for memory and cognitive functions), the caudate, putamen and globus pallidus (essential for motor control and executive function), the thalamus (vital for sensory and motor integration), the

corpus callosum (the primary white matter pathway for interhemispheric communication), and the lateral ventricles (important markers of brain development and structural integrity).

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Pediatric, MRI, low field MRI, quality assurance, image enhancement, segmentation, subcortical structures, deep gray structures, MICCAI, brain, neurodevelopment, Africa, South Asia

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

Our challenge is novel because it provides the first publicly available ultra-low-field (≈ 0.064 T) pediatric brain MRI dataset to develop deep learning algorithms for image quality assessment and enhancement, and downstream brain structure segmentation. Unlike traditional challenges that focus on high-field MRI, LISA specifically targets the unique difficulties of ultra-low-field MRI—such as poor contrast and low anatomical detail. Additionally, the datasets used in LISA are all from pediatric subject populations traditionally underrepresented at MICCAI (Pakistan, Uganda, South Africa).

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

The tasks of this challenge can be integrated at multiple stages of the ultra-low-field acquisition and analysis pipeline.

Task 1a (Image quality assessment) is designed for deployment both during acquisition and post hoc. In a real-time setting, the model can provide immediate, quantitative feedback to MRI technologists, flagging specific degradations such as subject motion, field inhomogeneity, or signal dropout as they occur, enabling reacquisition or protocol adjustment within the same scanning session. Retrospectively, the fine-grained quality scores produced by Task 1a can be applied to large existing ultra-low-field datasets to stratify scans by degradation type and severity, supporting systematic quality characterization and the identification of images suitable for recovery rather than exclusion.

Task 1b (Ultra-low-field image quality enhancement) enhancement models are applied selectively to correct motion-related artifacts, low signal-to-noise ratio, and contrast loss prior to any further preprocessing. This enables recovery of diagnostically and analytically usable images that would otherwise be discarded, improving data yield and consistency in both prospective studies and retrospective cohorts.

Task 2 (Brain segmentation) is used to extract anatomically defined brain structures from ultra-low-field MRI. The resulting segmentations enable computation of quantitative biomarkers such as regional brain volumes and shape-based measures, which can be used in downstream statistical analyses, longitudinal studies, or clinical research pipelines.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

MICCAI 2026

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

Full day

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

During the LISA 2025 Challenge, the growth in participation from 2024 led to a corresponding increase in strong submissions that, while not ranking among the winners, nevertheless demonstrated significant innovation and merit. As the LISA Challenge enters its third year, we anticipate continued expansion in both the scale and quality of submissions. Allocating additional time for the event would enable more comprehensive engagement with the presented work, encourage richer technical and scientific exchanges among participants, and enhance the visibility and influence of the challenge within the broader imaging research community.

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

MICCAI 2024 and 2025's LISA challenge supported 39 and 167 participants, respectively. We also collaborated with RISE-MICCAI to open a RISE-MICCAI only subset of the LISA challenge which supported over 108 additional participants in 2025. Considering the growth in LISA's first two years after publicity and outreach, we expect to receive at least 225 participants this year.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Yes

MICCAI LNCS proceedings

Indicate if you want to offer MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings to the participants. Publishing a proceedings volume is optional and at the discretion of each challenge's organizers. At a minimum, organizers must ensure that a description of each participant's submission is publicly available. Organizers who wish to publish MICCAI Springer LNCS proceedings must adhere to the MICCAI Satellite events publication process.

Yes

Collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR)

In collaboration with European Society of Radiology (ESR), we announce special clinical interest topics with associated clinicians who can help with the preparation of the proposals; the best 3 challenge proposals on these topics will get the opportunity to present their challenges at the European Congress of Radiology (ECR) 2027 in a special session. If you want to organize a challenge in collaboration with ESR on one of these topics, please reach out to the MICCAI Challenges Team ([miccai-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de](mailto:micca-challenges-2026@dkfz-heidelberg.de)) and we will put you in contact with the corresponding clinician.

Challenge in collaboration with ESR. Ticking 'Yes' implies that the challenge has been prepared in collaboration with the clinical contact point.

No

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

The LISA challenge will be run through the Sage Bionetworks' Synapse platform. During MICCAI 2026, we will need a projector, loud speakers and microphones for the winning participants to present their work.

TASK 1: 1a : Quality assessment of low field neonatal MR images

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

During the initial stages of life the human brain undergoes rapid tissue growth and development after birth. Accurately capturing and describing structural changes from magnetic resonance images (MRI) during this vital period is crucial for gaining new perspectives on healthy brain development and enabling the early identification of neurodevelopmental disorders.

While validated brain automatic quality analysis tools exist for adult brains, efforts to directly translate existing adult brain algorithms to pediatric MRI have generally failed. This is partly due to the poor gray/white matter differentiation of the developing brain and its rapid growth throughout the first years of life. In low and middle income countries, high field MRI systems are rare due to the high cost and maintenance required. More accessible MRI systems like the 0.064 T Hyperfine scanner would help to assess gross anatomical abnormalities. Despite the loss in image quality and challenges with image analysis, there are great advantages of using low field MRI including portability at the point of care of patients, small clinical costs with usability in low resource settings and elimination of sedation for young children.

To address the quality challenges in lowfield MRI, we introduce the first task of the Low-field pediatric brain magnetic resonance Image Segmentation and Quality Assurance (LISA) challenge, which focuses on the evaluation of objective quantifiable quality assurance QA methods. These methods will rate the overall quality of ultra low-field 0.064 T MRI and ensure that the acquired MRI meets specific accuracy and consistency standards in the provided data.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

pediatric, MRI, low field, quality assurance, MICCAI, brain, neurodevelopment, Africa, South Asia

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Natasha Lepore (1,4), Marius George Linguraru (2,3), Sean Deoni (6,7), Steven Williams (12), Jeffrey Tanedo (1), Rahimeh Rouhi (1), Austin Tapp (2), Krithika Iyer (2), Di Fan (1), Lauren Lee (1), Marvin Nelson(5), . Data Contributors: Victoria Nankabirwa(8)(9), Sean Deoni (6,7), Kirsty Donald (10), Sadia Parkar (11), Sidra Kaleem (11), Salman Osmani (11)

1 CIBORG Laboratory, Department of Radiology, Children's Hospital Los Angeles; 2 Sheikh Zayed Institute for Pediatric Surgical Innovation, Children's National Hospital; 3 Departments of Radiology and Pediatrics, George Washington University School of Medicine and Health Sciences; 4 Department of Pediatrics and Biomedical

Engineering, University of Southern California; 6 Advanced Baby Imaging Lab, Rhode Island Hospital; 7 Departments of Pediatrics and Diagnostic Radiology, Warren Alpert Medical School at Brown University; 8 Kawempe National Referral Hospital, Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda; 9 St. Francis Hospital - Nsambya, Kampala, Uganda ; 10 Department of Paediatrics and Child Health, University of Cape Town; 11 Aga Khan University Hospital ; 12 King's College London

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Natasha Lepore - nlepore@chla.usc.edu
Children's Hospital Los Angeles
4650 Sunset Blvd, Los Angeles, CA, 90027, USA
Department of Radiology and Imaging
Phone: 323-361-2411

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes, all three data acquisition teams in UCT, AKU, and MAK are led by clinicians and we work actively with them to develop clinically and research meaningful questions.

On the data processing and analysis side, Dr. Marvin Nelson advised and oversaw the development and refinement of the artifact assessment protocols defined in Task 1a and 1b.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

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b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

As with the LISA 2024 and 2025 Challenges, we plan to use the Synapse platform (SAGE Bionetworks; Synapse.org) for the challenge. This platform has been used for numerous other challenges, including the CBTN-CONNECT-DIPGr-ASNR-MICCAI Pediatric Brain Tumor Segmentation Challenge 2023, organized by Dr. Linguraru.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

synapse.org Synapse Project SynID is syn72118611. <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn72118611/wiki/637259>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding training samples, or including more training data as long as data is publicly available or will be made available after the challenge). Otherwise, only fully automatic methods are allowed.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Data used to train algorithms is not restricted to only the data provided by the challenge. Publicly available online and/or synthetic datasets are allowed. Our aim is to solve the segmentation and quality assurance of low-field MRI with the best possible tools. Investigator-owned data may be used only if data is made available to the community before July 21, 2026, which is when the testing phase begins.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

First prize in each task will be awarded \$1000 each.

Second prize in each task will be awarded \$500 each.

Third prize in each task will be awarded \$250 each.

Top three teams in each task will receive award certificates.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top three performing methods for each task will be announced publicly and these participants will be invited to present their method. All participant rankings (training, validation and testing) will also be made publicly available on the challenge website leaderboard. All participant methods that are ranked in the testing phase will have their accompanying short LNCS style paper (see publication policy section) made visible to organizers and challenge

participants. Making the participants' paper public will support methodological reproducibility and the open-source spirit the organizers seek to embody in this challenge.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Authors participating in the evaluation of their containerized model against the unseen test data are required to submit a short 8- to 11- page LNCS style paper through the LISA CMT by Friday, 29 May 2026 at 11:59 PM Pacific Time. Papers will be reviewed for suitability for online distribution. If challenge organizers deem that the method is not reproducible via the short paper instructions, then the method will not be evaluated and thus not considered for ranking. In some cases, organizers may provide comments to improve the short paper within the deadline. Details on training time and resources required to reproduce a participant's submission will be required in the short paper. Challenge participants must abide by the guiding principles for responsible research use and data handling within the Synapse Commons Platform as described in the Synapse Governance documents and by the Challenge's Official Rules. Publication embargo: Challenge participants are permitted to publish individual challenge results restricted to their own submitted method and ranking. Overall Challenge results or analysis thereof is restricted until Challenge organizers and participants have jointly published (or pre-published) an overview paper on the results and best performing strategies. The challenge organizers intend to aggregate the methods and summarize the results of LISA 2026 as a single journal manuscript with the goal of publication in journals of Medical Image Analysis, IEEE TMI, or a journal of similar impact factor. Participants will be contacted through Synapse-affiliated email addresses when this condition has been met. This information will also be posted within this Synapse project. Acknowledgement: Challenge participants and other data users are permitted to use, publish and present the Challenge results, after the embargo period, provided they acknowledge the LISA challenge organizing members as follows: "Data used in this publication were obtained as part of MICCAI 2026's Low field pediatric brain magnetic resonance Image Segmentation and quality Assurance (LISA) Challenge through Synapse ID syn72118611, Publications using challenge resources will be required to cite the overview paper of LISA 2026 and acknowledge the support of the Gates Foundation, which provided funding used for supporting data collection, curation, and processing.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Validation and Training Phase csv files with QC predictions are to be submitted on the Synapse Platform. Link to submission instructions for Task 1: <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn72118611/wiki/637256>

Test Phase submissions are done via Docker containers submitted on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn72118611/wiki/637259>

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to

compute challenge results.

To permit participant's method fine tuning, we will release the validation set in June (see timetable below). Validation ground truth data will not be released, but scores based on predictions will be provided to participants. Participants can select their final test submissions based on these validation results. After the validation phase ends, participants are allowed a maximum of 2 final testing submissions for each task, or 4 total submissions. The best scoring method of each task (2 methods per team) will be selected for final ranking. Neither test images nor their ground truths will be made public.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Friday, 3 April 2026

Challenge launch

Registration opens

Release of training data with ground truth labels

Friday, 24 April 2026

Release of validation data (without labels)

Validation phase opens

Friday, 29 May 2026

Validation phase ends (submission deadline of segmentation files)

Submission deadline of short papers in CMT, reporting method and preliminary results.

Tuesday, 2 June 2026

Testing phase opens

(available only to participants who submitted short papers)

Tuesday, 16 June 2026

Testing phase ends (submission deadline of Docker container)

Friday, 3 July 2026

Evaluation of Docker container on testing data ends

(performed by challenge organizers)

Tuesday, 7 July 2026

Top performing methods contacted for preparing oral presentation slides and camera extended paper submission, poster presenters invited

Tuesday, 28 July 2026

Camera-ready submission of extended papers for inclusion in the associated workshop proceedings due;
Confirmation of oral presentation and poster presentation acceptance

Tuesday, 11 August 2026

Camera-ready submission reviews sent out

Tuesday, 18 August 2026

Camera-ready submission review edits due

Sunday–Thursday, 4–8 October 2026

Presentation of Challenge, Announcement of the final top 3 ranked teams.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The low-high field magnetic resonance image data that will be used for the training, validation, and testing of algorithms was acquired through the UNITY project funded by the Gates Foundation (GF) at multiple international sites. Ethics approval was obtained at each site following the local standards and all data were fully de-identified before inclusion in the project. The protocol for releasing the data was approved by the institutional review board of the data contributing institution and data inclusion in the LISA challenge was approved by the GF. Training and validation data will be made available to challenge participants who agree to our terms and conditions through the Synapse website. Test data will be kept hidden from participants. LISA data will be available at the time of the challenge and beyond to increase its usability and impact.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Organizers' evaluation software, metrics and ranking code used for the challenge will be available on GitHub at: <https://github.com/LISACHallengeOfficial> and linked to our website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants must submit their containerized algorithm during the testing phase. Specific instructions for submission will be provided after challenge approval and will be detailed on the challenge website (Synapse). Participant containers will be made available for public use following the final testing/ranking phase of the challenge. Source code will be made available only at code authors' request.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

This challenge was funded by Gates Foundation grants INV-047887 and INV-087131 as part of the UNITY Consortium.

All challenge organizers and data contributors have ongoing access to the validation and test case labels.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research, Education, Training, Diagnosis, Intervention follow up, Intervention planning, Screening

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Classification, Recognition

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort will be all pediatric low field brain MRI.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort dataset will be healthy neonatal subjects approximately equal numbers of males and females scanned from the local population at :

- (1) University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa
- (2) Kawempe National Referral Hospital at Makerere University in Kampala, Uganda,
- (3) Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Ultra low field (0.064T) T2 MR images

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

For Task 1a, challengers will be given ratings of the usability of the data in the form of number ratings across 7 artifact categories.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No other information about the subject will be available.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Imaging data will consist of the pediatric brain and skull shown in low resolution magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) T2 data.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target will be ultra low field T2 brain MR images.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Sensitivity,Specificity,Precision,Robustness

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

For each data site, all low field images were obtained by scanning on a Hyperfine SWOOP, a 0.064T MR Scanner designed for FDA-approved portable brain imaging. The system is small enough to be put in patients' rooms and can be powered by standard electrical outlets. An attached Apple iPad handles postprocessing, from which,

clinically useful images may be obtained.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Low field images from Hyperfine SWOOP at all three sites

Magnetic field strength 0.064T, sequence type: spin echo, TR 1.5s, TE 5ms, TI 400ms

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Data was acquired at (1) University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa, (2) Kawempe National Referral Hospital, Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda, and. (3) Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All images were collected by trained personnel with experience imaging patients at the institutions listed above.

All quality assurance evaluations were performed by an expert medical image evaluator.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case encompasses a trio of anisotropic ultra low field T2 MR images and ratings in each of the 7 artifact classes.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

We will provide 760 images of which 532, 114, and 114 images will be considered for training, validation, and testing, respectively.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

100% of the data across the training, testing and validation cohorts are annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total number of cases has been determined based on the available data. We collected data from different sites to introduce diversity, thereby avoiding overfitting and achieving better generalizability for the proposed models in the tasks. To prevent overlap between scans from one subject in the training cohort and those in the validation and test cohorts (due to multiple scans from a single subject), we will consider subjects rather than individual scans during the data division for training and validation. We follow the standard division of data for

training (70%), validation (15%), and test (15%) and apply it to each site to get the final division for training, validation and test cohorts.

The number of subjects in training, validation and test cohorts is as follows. Each subject has three orthogonally acquired images (axial, sagittal, and coronal) - each with their own set of labels.

UCT, MAK and AKU with 187, 168, and 177 training images from each site for a total of 532 images with labels.

UCT, MAK and AKU with 39, 18, and 39 validation subjects respectively for a total of 96 images with labels.

UCT, MAK and AKU with 39, 18, and 39 test subjects respectively for a total of 96 images with labels.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All cases will be rated across 7 domains (motion, contrast, noise, zipper, FOV, banding, and distortion) in a three point scale (0,1,2).

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Three medical image evaluators were used to assess the quality of the data through manual image examination. A neuroradiologist reviewed and approved the assessment protocol.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The quality assessment protocol was based on the architecture found in [1] in order to rate motion, contrast, and noise. For the purpose of assessing the low field images, we also added categories for zipper, positioning banding, and distortion artifacts with the definitions below.

Zipper

0: no zipper

1: Zipper is visible around the brain and interferes with brain contrast

2: Zipper is visible and causes severe distortion with brain contrast

Positioning / Complete FOV

0: Skull and cortex are within FOV

1: Any portion of the skull is missing from FOV

2: Both skull and any portion of the cortex have been cut from FOV

Banding

0: No Banding

1: Banding across the MR image where tissue contrast is still visible

2: Severe banding where tissue contrast is no longer visible

Distortion

0: No distortion of the brain

1: Any slight distortion of the brain which interferes lightly with brain contrast

2: Any distortion of the brain which severely affects the contrast between structures

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The raters have many years of experience in assessing MR image quality. In addition, the protocols and subsets of the annotations were verified by Dr. Marvin Nelson, a pediatric neuroradiologist with 50+ years of experience.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All images were first converted to NIFTI from DICOM using dcm2nii. These low field images are defaced for full anonymization using our defacing pipeline which is available in our github repository located here - <https://github.com/LISACHallengeOfficial/2025Preprocessing/tree/main>

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

We will provide intra-rater reliability scores to estimate the magnitude of human error in image annotation.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We will employ five distinct metrics including accuracy, F1 score, F2 score, precision, and recall.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Metric choices were based on recommendations found in [4], ensuring magnetic resonance imaging samples meet minimum quality requirements and contain no significant image artifacts.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

We will take the mean across their respective metrics to obtain rankings. Standard deviations will also be calculated and given.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Submissions that have missing results or cannot provide results because inference fails on a test case will be assigned the lowest possible score for the failed test case using metrics relevant to the task. For example, if a missing result or failed inference occurs in Task 1a, the values for accuracy, F1 score, F2 score, precision, and recall would all be set to 0.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The ranking system described will be used to obtain a fair and complete comparison across all metrics between participants. We desire a ranking scheme that is empirical, objective, and provides both participants and organizers with a clear understanding of the 'best' challenge solution.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Permutational analysis will be employed to evaluate uncertainties in rankings. Each team's QA performance will be assessed for all 7 artifact classes, considering each metric. Rankings for the measures will be combined by averaging, and statistical significance will be assessed exclusively for QA performance measures. This assessment will involve permuting the relative ranks for each QA measure, considering each artifact class for QA per subject in the testing data. In addition, deeper insights into performance differences among participating models will be obtained through pairwise comparisons performed within a bootstrap framework, thereby complementing the permutation-based ranking assessment and ensuring a consistent and robust evaluation of statistical significance. This permutation testing would reflect differences in performance that exceeded those that might be expected by chance

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

The precision of performance estimates for individual algorithms will be assessed using percentile bootstrap confidence intervals on the held-out test set. Test cases will be resampled with replacement while keeping the sample size fixed, and performance metrics (accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and F2-score) will be recomputed for each bootstrap resample using aggregated confusion-matrix counts. In addition to reporting individual metrics, an overall average across all evaluation metrics will be computed as a summary measure. The

metric values computed on the full test set will be reported as point estimates, and the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the bootstrap distribution will be reported as the 95% confidence interval.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across test cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Performance variability across test cases will be assessed by reporting the standard deviation of per-case performance metrics. This will provide a descriptive measure of how algorithm performance varies across different test cases. Where appropriate, additional summary statistics or visualizations (e.g., boxplots) may be used to further illustrate performance distributions.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Algorithm rankings are based on an overall QA score defined as the unweighted mean of accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and F2-score computed on the test set. To assess ranking variability, bootstrap resampling of the test cases is performed. For each bootstrap iteration, test cases are resampled with replacement, performance metrics are recomputed from aggregated confusion-matrix counts, the overall QA score is calculated, and algorithms are ranked accordingly. This results in a distribution of ranks for each algorithm across bootstrap iterations. Ranking stability is assessed using the median rank and interquartile range derived from this distribution.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Statistical differences between algorithms can also be assessed within the same bootstrap framework. For each pair of algorithms, the difference in the overall QA score is calculated across bootstrap resamples, yielding a distribution of score differences. A 95% percentile confidence interval (CI) for this difference is derived from the distribution. A performance difference is considered statistically significant if the corresponding confidence interval does not include zero. To account for multiple pairwise comparisons across all participating teams, p-values derived from the bootstrap distributions are adjusted using the Holm-Bonferroni procedure with a significance level of $\alpha=0.05$.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

All test cases are required to be present for all participating teams. If a team fails to produce a result for a case, that case will be treated as missing for that team and will be assigned the worst possible score for that metric for ranking purposes. This avoids inflating performance estimates and ensures comparability across participants. No subject-level data will be removed from evaluation.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Python (NumPy, SciPy, Pandas) and Synapse platform (for data hosting, submission management, and automated evaluation)

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or

- ranking variability.

N/A

TASK 2: 1b: Quality improvement of low field neonatal MR images

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

During the initial stages of life the human brain undergoes rapid tissue growth and development after birth. Accurately capturing and describing structural changes from magnetic resonance images (MRI) during this vital period is crucial for gaining new perspectives on healthy brain development and enabling the early identification of neurodevelopmental disorders.

While validated brain automatic quality analysis tools exist for adult brains, efforts to directly translate existing adult brain algorithms to pediatric MRI have generally failed. This is partly due to the poor gray/white matter differentiation of the developing brain and its rapid growth throughout the first years of life. In low and middle income countries, high field MRI systems are rare due to the high cost and maintenance required. More accessible MRI systems like the 0.064 T Hyperfine scanner would help to assess gross anatomical abnormalities; structural delineation challenges are further compounded in these lower resolution imaging environments. Despite the loss in image quality and challenges with image analysis, there are great advantages of using low field MRI including portability at the point of care of patients, small clinical costs with usability in low resource settings and elimination of sedation for young children.

To address the quality challenges in ultra low-field MRI, we expand the first task of the Lowfield pediatric brain magnetic resonance Image Segmentation and Quality Assurance (LISA) challenge, to focus on the development of methods to reduce the severity of noise and motion artifacts and thus improve the SNR of uLF MR images. In Task 1b, participants will have access to Task 1a's dataset of uLF images with corresponding noise and motion artifact ratings and will be expected to develop unsupervised methods to transform artifacted images affected by noise and motion into uLF images consistent with the noise- and motion- artifact free images in Task 1a's dataset. The objective of Task 1b is thus to produce images which would be rated as "artifact-free" under Task 1a's assessment criteria without reliance on pixel-aligned ground truth pairs or high field references.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

pediatric, MRI, low field, quality improvement, MICCAI, brain, neurodevelopment, Africa, South Asia

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Natasha Lepore (1,4), Marius George Linguraru (2,3), Sean Deoni (6,7), Steven Williams (12), Jeffrey Tanedo (1), Rahimeh Rouhi (1), Austin Tapp (2), Krithika Iyer (2), Di Fan (1), Lauren Lee (1), Marvin Nelson(5), . Data Contributors: Victoria Nankabirwa(8)(9), Sean Deoni (6,7), Kirsty Donald (10), Sadia Parkar (11), Sidra Kaleem (11), Salman Osmani (11)

1 CIBORG Laboratory, Department of Radiology, Children's Hospital Los Angeles; 2 Sheikh Zayed Institute for Pediatric Surgical Innovation, Children's National Hospital; 3 Departments of Radiology and Pediatrics, George Washington University School of Medicine and Health Sciences; 4 Department of Pediatrics and Biomedical Engineering, University of Southern California; 6 Advanced Baby Imaging Lab, Rhode Island Hospital; 7 Departments of Pediatrics and Diagnostic Radiology, Warren Alpert Medical School at Brown University; 8 Kawempe National Referral Hospital, Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda; 9 St. Francis Hospital - Nsambya, Kampala, Uganda ; 10 Department of Paediatrics and Child Health, University of Cape Town; 11 Aga Khan University Hospital ; 12 King's College London

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Natasha Lepore - nlepore@chla.usc.edu
Children's Hospital Los Angeles
4650 Sunset Blvd, Los Angeles, CA, 90027, USA
Department of Radiology and Imaging
Phone: 323-361-2411

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes, all three data acquisition teams in UCT, AKU, and MAK are led by clinicians and we work actively with them to develop clinically and research meaningful questions.

On the data processing and analysis side, Dr. Marvin Nelson advised and oversaw the development and refinement of the artifact assessment protocols defined in Task 1a and 1b.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

As with the LISA 2024 and 2025 Challenges, we plan to use the Synapse platform (SAGE Bionetworks; Synapse.org) for the challenge. This platform has been used for numerous other challenges, including the

CBTN-CONNECT-DIPGr-ASNR-MICCAI Pediatric Brain Tumor Segmentation Challenge 2023, organized by Dr. Linguraru.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

synapse.org Synapse Project SynID is syn72118611. <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn72118611/wiki/637259>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding training samples, or including more training data as long as data is publicly available or will be made available after the challenge). Otherwise, only fully automatic methods are allowed.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Data used to train algorithms is not restricted to only the data provided by the challenge. Publicly available online and/or synthetic datasets are allowed. Our aim is to solve the segmentation and quality assurance of low-field MRI with the best possible tools. Investigator-owned data may be used only if data is made available to the community before July 21, 2026, which is when the testing phase begins.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

First prize in each task will be awarded \$1000 each.

Second prize in each task will be awarded \$500 each.

Third prize in each task will be awarded \$250 each.

Top three teams in each task will receive award certificates.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top three performing methods for each task will be announced publicly and these participants will be invited to present their method. All participant rankings (training, validation and testing) will also be made publicly available on the challenge website leaderboard. All participant methods that are ranked in the testing phase will have their accompanying short LNCS style paper (see publication policy section) made visible to organizers and challenge participants. Making the participants' paper public will support methodological reproducibility and the open-source spirit the organizers seek to embody in this challenge.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Authors participating in the evaluation of their containerized model against the unseen test data are required to submit a short 8- to 11- page LNCS style paper through the LISA CMT by Friday, 29 May 2026 at 11:59 PM Pacific Time. Papers will be reviewed for suitability for online distribution. If challenge organizers deem that the method is not reproducible via the short paper instructions, then the method will not be evaluated and thus not considered for ranking. In some cases, organizers may provide comments to improve the short paper within the deadline. Details on training time and resources required to reproduce a participant's submission will be required in the short paper. Challenge participants must abide by the guiding principles for responsible research use and data handling within the Synapse Commons Platform as described in the Synapse Governance documents and by the Challenge's Official Rules. Publication embargo: Challenge participants are permitted to publish individual challenge results restricted to their own submitted method and ranking. Overall Challenge results or analysis thereof is restricted until Challenge organizers and participants have jointly published (or pre-published) an overview paper on the results and best performing strategies. The challenge organizers intend to aggregate the methods and summarize the results of LISA 2026 as a single journal manuscript with the goal of publication in journals of Medical Image Analysis, IEEE TMI, or a journal of similar impact factor. Participants will be contacted through Synapse-affiliated email addresses when this condition has been met. This information will also be posted within this Synapse project. Acknowledgement: Challenge participants and other data users are permitted to use, publish and present the Challenge results, after the embargo period, provided they acknowledge the LISA challenge organizing members as follows: "Data used in this publication were obtained as part of MICCAI 2026's Low field pediatric brain magnetic resonance Image Segmentation and quality Assurance (LISA) Challenge through Synapse ID syn72118611, Publications using challenge resources will be required to cite the overview paper of LISA 2026 and acknowledge the support of the Gates Foundation, which provided funding used for supporting data collection, curation, and processing.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Validation and Training Phase prediction images are to be submitted on the Synapse Platform. Link to submission instructions: <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn72118611/wiki/637256>

Test Phase submissions are done via Docker containers submitted on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn72118611/wiki/637259>

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

To permit participant's method fine tuning, we will release the validation set in June (see timetable below). Validation enhanced or artifact-free data will not be released, but scores based on predictions will be provided to participants. Participants can select their final test submissions based on these validation results. After the validation phase ends, participants are allowed a maximum of 2 final testing submissions for each task, or 4 total submissions. The best scoring method of each task (2 methods per team) will be selected for final ranking. Neither test images nor their ground truths will be made public.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Friday, 3 April 2026

Challenge launch

Registration opens

Release of training data with ground truth labels

Friday, 24 April 2026

Release of validation data (without labels)

Validation phase opens

Friday, 29 May 2026

Validation phase ends (submission deadline of segmentation files)

Submission deadline of short papers in CMT, reporting method and preliminary results.

Tuesday, 2 June 2026

Testing phase opens

(available only to participants who submitted short papers)

Tuesday, 16 June 2026

Testing phase ends (submission deadline of Docker container)

Friday, 3 July 2026

Evaluation of Docker container on testing data ends
(performed by challenge organizers)

Tuesday, 7 July 2026

Top performing methods contacted for preparing oral presentation slides and camera extended paper submission, poster presenters invited

Tuesday, 28 July 2026

Camera-ready submission of extended papers for inclusion in the associated workshop proceedings due;
Confirmation of oral presentation and poster presentation acceptance

Tuesday, 11 August 2026

Camera-ready submission reviews sent out

Tuesday, 18 August 2026

Camera-ready submission review edits due

Sunday–Thursday, 4–8 October 2026

Presentation of Challenge, Announcement of the final top 3 ranked teams.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The low-high field magnetic resonance image data that will be used for the training, validation, and testing of algorithms was acquired through the UNITY project funded by the Gates Foundation (GF) at multiple international sites. Ethics approval was obtained at each site following the local standards and all data were fully de-identified before inclusion in the project. The protocol for releasing the data was approved by the institutional review board of the data contributing institution and data inclusion in the LISA challenge was approved by the GF. Training and validation data will be made available to challenge participants who agree to our terms and conditions through the Synapse website. Test data will be kept hidden from participants. LISA data will be available at the time of the challenge and beyond to increase its usability and impact.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)

- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Organizers' evaluation software, metrics and ranking code used for the challenge will be available on GitHub at: <https://github.com/LISACHallengeOfficial> and linked to our website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants must submit their containerized algorithm during the testing phase. Specific instructions for submission will be provided after challenge approval and will be detailed on the challenge website (Synapse). Participant containers will be made available for public use following the final testing/ranking phase of the challenge. Source code will be made available only at code authors' request.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

This challenge was funded by Gates Foundation grants INV-047887 and INV-087131 as part of the UNITY Consortium.

All challenge organizers and data contributors have ongoing access to the validation and test case labels.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis

- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research, Education, Training, Screening

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Enhancement, Reconstruction, Image Translation, Modeling

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort will be all pediatric low field brain MRI.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort dataset will be healthy neonatal subjects approximately equal numbers of males and females scanned from the local population at :

- (1) University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa
- (2) Kawempe National Referral Hospital at Makerere University in Kampala, Uganda,
- (3) Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Ultra low field (0.064T) T2 MR images

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

For Task 1b, participants will use Task 1a's dataset of annotations in the form of number ratings across 7 artifact categories. Additionally, we will provide a CSV file which organizes Task 1a's dataset into four categories 1) No Noise + No Motion, 2) With Noise + No Motion, 3) No Noise + With Motion, and 4) With Noise + With Motion

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No other information about the subject will be available.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Imaging data will consist of the pediatric brain and skull shown in low resolution magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) T2 data.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target will be low field T2 brain MR images.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Image Fidelity, Perceptual Quality, Information Preservation, Robustness

DATA SETS**Data source(s)**

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

For each data site, all low field images were obtained by scanning on a Hyperfine SWOOP, a 0.064T MR Scanner designed for FDA-approved portable brain imaging. The system is small enough to be put in patients' rooms and can be powered by standard electrical outlets. An attached Apple iPad handles postprocessing, from which, clinically useful images may be obtained.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Low field images from Hyperfine SWOOP at all three sites

Magnetic field strength 0.064T, sequence type: spin echo, TR 1.5s, TE 5ms, TI 400ms

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Data was acquired at (1) University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa, (2) Kawempe National Referral Hospital, Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda, and. (3) Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All images were collected by trained personnel with experience imaging patients at the institutions listed above. All quality assurance evaluations were performed by an expert medical image evaluator.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case encompasses a single anisotropic ultra low field T2 MR image and the image's ratings in each of the 7 artifact classes.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

We will provide 760 images of which 532, 114, and 114 images will be considered for training, validation, and testing, respectively.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

100% of the data across the training, testing and validation cohorts are annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total number of cases has been determined based on the available data. We collected data from different sites to introduce diversity, thereby avoiding overfitting and achieving better generalizability for the proposed models in the tasks. To prevent overlap between scans from one subject in the training cohort and those in the validation and test cohorts (due to multiple scans from a single subject), we will consider subjects rather than individual scans during the data division for training and validation. We follow the standard division of data for training (70%), validation (15%), and test (15%) and apply it to each site to get the final division for training, validation and test cohorts.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All cases will be rated across 7 domains (motion, contrast, noise, zipper, FOV, banding, and distortion) in a three point scale (0,1,2).

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Three medical image evaluators were used to assess the quality of the data through manual image examination. A neuroradiologist reviewed and approved the assessment protocol.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The quality assessment protocol was based on the architecture found in [1] in order to rate motion, contrast, and noise. For the purpose of assessing the low field images, we also added categories for zipper, positioning banding, and distortion artifacts with the definitions below.

Zipper

0: no zipper

1: Zipper is visible around the brain and interferes with brain contrast

2: Zipper is visible and causes severe distortion with brain contrast

Positioning / Complete FOV

0: Skull and cortex are within FOV

1: Any portion of the skull is missing from FOV

2: Both skull and any portion of the cortex have been cut from FOV

Banding

0: No Banding

1: Banding across the MR image where tissue contrast is still visible

2: Severe banding where tissue contrast is no longer visible

Distortion

0: No distortion of the brain

1: Any slight distortion of the brain which interferes lightly with brain contrast

2: Any distortion of the brain which severely affects the contrast between structures

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The raters have many years of experience in assessing MR image quality. In addition, the protocols and subsets of the annotations were verified by Dr. Marvin Nelson, a pediatric neuroradiologist with 50+ years of experience.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All images were first converted to NIFTI from DICOM using dcm2nii. These low field images are defaced for full anonymization using our defacing pipeline which is available in our github repository located here - <https://github.com/LISACChallengeOfficial/2025Preprocessing/tree/main>

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

We will provide intra-rater reliability scores to estimate the magnitude of human error in image annotation.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS**Metric(s)**

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We will employ 3 distinct metrics: Frechet Inception Distance (FID), Peak-signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR), Learned Patch Image Perceptual Similarity (LPIPS)

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Metric choices were based on prior challenges that perform image-to-image translation tasks and evaluate the perceptual and voxel-level quality of the predicted image compared to its ground truth image (SynthRAD challenge: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1361841524002019>). Additional works on image reconstruction and enhancement metrics in the field utilize these metrics for super-resolution tasks evaluation (our MICCAI 20245 paper: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/40297805/>).

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

We will take the normalized mean across their respective metrics to obtain rankings. Standard deviations will also be calculated and given. For unbounded metrics such as FID and PSNR, normalization will be performed using cohort-level min-max scaling across all participants rather than per-participant scaling.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Submissions that have missing results or cannot provide results because inference fails on a test case will be assigned the lowest possible score for the failed test case using metrics relevant to the task. For example, if a missing result or failed inference occurs in Task 1b, the values for PSNR would be set to 0.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The ranking system described will be used to obtain a fair and complete comparison across all metrics between participants. We desire a ranking scheme that is empirical, objective, and provides both participants and organizers with a clear understanding of the 'best' challenge solution.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Permutational analyses will be employed to evaluate uncertainties in rankings. Each team's model performance will be assessed using three complementary metrics: FID, PSNR, and LPIPS. Because these metrics operate on different scales and directions, each metric will first be normalized to a common 0–1 range across all submissions, with direction inverted where lower values indicate better performance. For each method, an overall quality-improvement score will then be computed as the mean of the normalized metrics. To evaluate the robustness of rankings derived from this composite score, permutation testing will be applied by repeatedly permuting team labels across subjects and recomputing rankings. In addition, deeper insights into performance differences among participating models will be obtained through pairwise comparisons performed within a bootstrap framework, thereby complementing the permutation-based ranking assessment and ensuring a consistent and statistically rigorous evaluation of performance differences. This permutation testing would reflect differences in performance that exceeded those that might be expected by chance

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the

accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

The precision of performance estimates for individual algorithms will be assessed using percentile bootstrap confidence intervals on the held-out test set. Test cases will be resampled with replacement while keeping the sample size fixed, and the performance metrics (FID, PSNR, and LPIPS) will be recomputed for each bootstrap resample. In addition to reporting each metric individually, a composite score will be obtained as the mean of the normalized metrics. For both the individual metrics and the composite score, the value computed on the full test set will be reported as the point estimate, and the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the bootstrap distribution will be reported as the corresponding 95% confidence interval.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across tests cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Performance variability across test cases will be assessed by reporting the standard deviation of per-case performance metrics. This will provide a descriptive measure of how algorithm performance varies across different test cases. Where appropriate, additional summary statistics or visualizations (e.g., boxplots) may be used to further illustrate performance distributions.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Algorithm rankings will be based on a composite score defined as the mean of the normalized image-quality metrics (FID, PSNR, and LPIPS). To assess ranking variability, bootstrap resampling of the test cases will be performed. For each bootstrap iteration, test cases will be resampled with replacement, performance metrics will be recomputed, the composite score will be recalculated, and algorithms will be ranked accordingly. This procedure yields a distribution of ranks for each algorithm across bootstrap iterations. Ranking stability will then be assessed using the median rank and interquartile range derived from this distribution.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

Statistical differences between algorithms will also be assessed within the same bootstrap framework. For each pair of algorithms, the difference in the composite image-quality score (mean of normalized FID, PSNR and LPIPS) will be computed across bootstrap resamples, yielding a distribution of score differences. A 95% percentile confidence interval (CI) for this difference will then be derived from the bootstrap distribution. A performance difference will be considered statistically significant if the corresponding confidence interval does not include zero. To account for multiple pairwise comparisons across participating teams, p-values obtained from the bootstrap distributions will be adjusted using the Holm–Bonferroni procedure with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

All test cases are required to be present for all participating teams. If a team fails to produce a result for a case, that case will be treated as missing for that team and will be assigned the worst possible score for that metric for ranking purposes. This avoids inflating performance estimates and ensures comparability across participants. No subject-level data will be removed from evaluation.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Python (NumPy, SciPy, Pandas) and Synapse platform (for data hosting, submission management, and automated evaluation)

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

TASK 3: 2: Segmentation of subcortical structures from low field neonatal MR images

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

During the initial stages of life, the human brain undergoes rapid tissue growth and development after birth. Accurately capturing and describing structural changes from magnetic resonance images (MRI) during this vital period is crucial for gaining new perspectives on healthy brain development and enabling the early identification of neurodevelopmental disorders.

While validated brain segmentation tools exist for adult brains, efforts to directly translate existing adult brain algorithms to pediatric MRI have generally failed. This is partly due to the poor gray/white matter differentiation of the developing brain and its rapid growth throughout the first years of life. These challenges impair the ability of existing algorithms to accurately segment pediatric brain structures even with high field (1.5T or 3T) MRI systems.

In low and middle-income countries, high field MRI systems are rare, due to the cost and maintenance required. More accessible MRI systems like the 0.064T Hyperfine scanner would help to assess gross anatomical abnormalities; structural delineation challenges are further compounded in these lower resolution imaging environments. Despite the loss in image quality and challenges with image analysis, there are great advantages of using low field MRI, including portability at the point of care of patients, small clinical costs with usability in low resource settings, and elimination of sedation for young children.

To drive advancements in automatic segmentation methods for low-field MRI, the LISA challenge introduces the second task. Participants are tasked with developing and evaluating deep learning methods for the automatic segmentation of several subcortical structures - the hippocampi, caudate nuclei, putamen and globus pallidus complex, thalamus, corpus callosum and frontal lateral ventricles in ultra low field (0.064T) T2-weighted magnetic resonance images of the healthy brain in early childhood.

The LISA challenge provides challenge participants with the first-ever publicly available ultra low-field MRI dataset with anatomical annotations, ensuring that the training, validation, and testing phases utilize the same dataset obtained from the Synapse platform. The overarching goal of the entire challenge is obtaining optimal deep learning tools for the assessment and segmentation of low-field MRI images in early childhood.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

pediatric, MRI, low field segmentation, subcortical, hippocampus, basal ganglia, caudate nuclei, putamen, globus pallidus, lentiform nuclei, thalamus, corpus callosum, lateral ventricles, MICCAI, brain, neurodevelopment, Africa, South Asia

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Natasha Lepore (1,4), Marius George Linguraru (2,3), Sean Deoni (6,7), Steven Williams (12), Jeffrey Tanedo (1), Rahimeh Rouhi (1), Austin Tapp (2), Krithika Iyer (2), Di Fan (1), Lauren Lee (1), Marvin Nelson(5), . Data Contributors: Victoria Nankabirwa(8)(9), Sean Deoni (6,7), Kirsty Donald (10), Sadia Parkar (11), Sidra Kaleem (11), Salman Osmani (11)

1 CIBORG Laboratory, Department of Radiology, Children's Hospital Los Angeles; 2 Sheikh Zayed Institute for Pediatric Surgical Innovation, Children's National Hospital; 3 Departments of Radiology and Pediatrics, George Washington University School of Medicine and Health Sciences; 4 Department of Pediatrics and Biomedical Engineering, University of Southern California; 6 Advanced Baby Imaging Lab, Rhode Island Hospital; 7 Departments of Pediatrics and Diagnostic Radiology, Warren Alpert Medical School at Brown University; 8 Kawempe National Referral Hospital, Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda; 9 St. Francis Hospital - Nsambya, Kampala, Uganda ; 10 Department of Paediatrics and Child Health, University of Cape Town; 11 Aga Khan University Hospital ; 12 King's College London

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Natasha Lepore - nlepore@chla.usc.edu
 Children's Hospital Los Angeles
 4650 Sunset Blvd, Los Angeles, CA, 90027, USA
 Department of Radiology and Imaging
 Phone: 323-361-2411

c) Indicate whether clinicians are part of the organizing team. If yes, describe their role.

Yes, all three data acquisition teams in UCT, AKU, and MAK are led by clinicians and we work actively with them to develop clinically and research meaningful questions.

On the data processing and analysis side, Dr. Marvin Nelson advised and oversaw the development and refinement of the anatomical segmentation protocols described in Task 2.

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2026

b) Report the platform used to run the challenge.

As with the LISA 2024 and 2025 Challenges, we plan to use the Synapse platform (SAGE Bionetworks; Synapse.org) for the challenge. This platform has been used for numerous other challenges, including the CBTN-CONNECT-DIPGr-ASNR-MICCAI Pediatric Brain Tumor Segmentation Challenge 2023, organized by Dr. Linguraru.

c) Do you agree that the your submission is shared with the platform (e.g., grand-challenge, synapse...) that you indicated?

Please note: 1) this purpose of such sharing is that the challenge chairs and the platform can communicate smoothly, your answer won't impact the review of your proposal; 2) regardless of your response to this question, it is your responsibility to perform all actions required by the platform (e.g. filling their submission request).

Yes

d) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

synapse.org Synapse Project SynID is syn72118611. <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn72118611/wiki/637259>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed. This includes the policy regarding any curation, (pre-)processing and (pre-)training steps.

User interaction is allowed for curating training data (i.e. excluding training samples, or including more training data as long as data is publicly available or will be made available after the challenge). Otherwise, only fully automatic methods are allowed.

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or may also include publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets. Clarify whether such additional data needs to be publicly available at the time of the challenge launch. Clarify whether adding (private) annotations of the public data is allowed.

Data used to train algorithms is not restricted to only the data provided by the challenge. Publicly available online and/or synthetic datasets are allowed. Our aim is to solve the segmentation and quality assurance of low-field MRI with the best possible tools. Investigator -owned data may be used only if data is made available to the community before July 21, 2026, which is when the testing phase begins.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

First prize in each task will be awarded \$1000 each.

Second prize in each task will be awarded \$500 each.

Third prize in each task will be awarded \$250 each.

Top three teams in each task will receive award certificates.

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top three performing methods for each task will be announced publicly and these participants will be invited to present their method. All participant rankings (training, validation and testing) will also be made publicly available on the challenge website leaderboard. All participant methods that are ranked in the testing phase will have their accompanying short LNCS style paper (see publication policy section) made visible to organizers and challenge participants. Making the participants' paper public will support methodological reproducibility and the open-source spirit the organizers seek to embody in this challenge.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Authors participating in the evaluation of their containerized model against the unseen test data are required to submit a short 8- to 11- page LNCS style paper through the LISA CMT by Friday, 29 May 2026 at 11:59 PM Pacific Time. Papers will be reviewed for suitability for online distribution. If challenge organizers deem that the method is not reproducible via the short paper instructions, then the method will not be evaluated and thus not considered for ranking. In some cases, organizers may provide comments to improve the short paper within the deadline. Details on training time and resources required to reproduce a participant's submission will be required in the short paper. Challenge participants must abide by the guiding principles for responsible research use and data handling within the Synapse Commons Platform as described in the Synapse Governance documents and by the Challenge's Official Rules. Publication embargo: Challenge participants are permitted to publish individual challenge results restricted to their own submitted method and ranking. Overall Challenge results or analysis thereof is restricted until Challenge organizers and participants have jointly published (or pre-published) an overview paper on the results and best performing strategies. The challenge organizers intend to aggregate the methods and summarize the results of LISA 2026 as a single journal manuscript with the goal of publication in journals of Medical Image Analysis, IEEE TMI, or a journal of similar impact factor. Participants will be contacted through Synapse-affiliated email addresses when this condition has been met. This information will also be posted within this Synapse project. Acknowledgement: Challenge participants and other data users are permitted to use, publish and present the Challenge results, after the embargo period, provided they acknowledge the LISA challenge organizing members as follows: "Data used in this publication were obtained as part of MICCAI 2026's Low field pediatric brain magnetic resonance Image Segmentation and quality Assurance (LISA) Challenge through Synapse ID syn72118611, Publications using challenge resources will be required to cite the overview paper of LISA 2026 and acknowledge the support of the Gates Foundation, which provided funding used for supporting data collection, curation, and processing.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Validation and Training Phase prediction images are to be submitted on the Synapse Platform. Link to submission instructions: <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn72118611/wiki/637256>

Test Phase submissions are done via Docker containers submitted on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn72118611/wiki/637259>

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

To permit participant's method fine tuning, we will release the validation set in June (see timetable below). Validation ground truth data will not be released, but scores based on predictions will be provided to participants. Participants can select their final test submissions based on these validation results. After the validation phase ends, participants are allowed a maximum of 2 final testing submissions for each task, or 4 total submissions. The best scoring method of each task (2 methods per team) will be selected for final ranking. Neither test images nor their ground truths will be made public.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Friday, 3 April 2026

Challenge launch

Registration opens

Release of training data with ground truth labels

Friday, 24 April 2026

Release of validation data (without labels)

Validation phase opens

Friday, 29 May 2026

Validation phase ends (submission deadline of segmentation files)

Submission deadline of short papers in CMT, reporting method and preliminary results.

Tuesday, 2 June 2026

Testing phase opens

(available only to participants who submitted short papers)

Tuesday, 16 June 2026

Testing phase ends (submission deadline of Docker container)

Friday, 3 July 2026

Evaluation of Docker container on testing data ends

(performed by challenge organizers)

Tuesday, 7 July 2026

Top performing methods contacted for preparing oral presentation slides and camera extended paper submission, poster presenters invited

Tuesday, 28 July 2026

Camera-ready submission of extended papers for inclusion in the associated workshop proceedings due;

Confirmation of oral presentation and poster presentation acceptance

Tuesday, 11 August 2026

Camera-ready submission reviews sent out

Tuesday, 18 August 2026

Camera-ready submission review edits due

Sunday–Thursday, 4–8 October 2026

Presentation of Challenge, Announcement of the final top 3 ranked teams.

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The low-high field magnetic resonance image data that will be used for the training, validation, and testing of algorithms was acquired through the UNITY project funded by the Gates Foundation (GF) at multiple international sites. Ethics approval was obtained at each site following the local standards and all data were fully de-identified before inclusion in the project. The protocol for releasing the data was approved by the institutional review board of the data contributing institution and data inclusion in the LISA challenge was approved by the GF. Training and validation data will be made available to challenge participants who agree to our terms and conditions through the Synapse website. Test data will be kept hidden from participants. LISA data will be available at the time of the challenge and beyond to increase its usability and impact.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

Please note that the data license should not differ among sources. In case a license has to be changed, it has to be reported to the MICCAI challenges team and changed in the proposal.

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

Organizers' evaluation software, metrics and ranking code used for the challenge will be available on GitHub at: <https://github.com/LISACHallengeOfficial> and linked to our website.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

Participants must submit their containerized algorithm during the testing phase. Specific instructions for submission will be provided after challenge approval and will be detailed on the challenge website (Synapse). Participant containers will be made available for public use following the final testing/ranking phase of the challenge. Source code will be made available only at code authors' request.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

This challenge was funded by Gates Foundation grants INV-047887 and INV-087131 as part of the UNITY Consortium.

All challenge organizers and data contributors have ongoing access to the validation and test case labels.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis

- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research, Education, Training, Diagnosis, Intervention Assistance, Intervention follow up, Intervention planning, Screening

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort will be all pediatric low field brain MRI.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort dataset will be healthy neonatal subjects approximately equal numbers of males and females scanned from the local population at :

(1) University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa

(2) Kawempe National Referral Hospital at Makerere University in Kampala, Uganda,

(3) Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Low field (0.064T) T2 MR images and ONLY segmentations derived from matching high field (3T or 1.5T) T2 MR images

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

For Task 2, challengers will have access to manually segmented subcortical structure data (bilateral hippocampi, caudate nuclei, putamen and globus pallidus complex, thalamus, corpus callosum, frontal lateral ventricles) from matching high field data.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No other information about the subject will be available.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Imaging data will consist of the pediatric brain and skull shown in low resolution magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) T2 data. For Task 2, there will also be a set of manually corrected bilateral hippocampi, caudate nuclei, putamen and globus pallidus complex, thalamus, corpus callosum, frontal lateral ventricles.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target will be MRI subcortical segmentations, including: bilateral hippocampi, caudate nuclei, putamen and globus pallidus complex, thalamus, corpus callosum, frontal lateral ventricles. These structures will be annotated from high field images, and obtained from matching low field T2 brain MR images.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below,

parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Precision, Consistency, Reliability

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

For each data site, all low field images were obtained by scanning on a Hyperfine SWOOP, a 0.064T MR Scanner designed for FDA-approved portable brain imaging. The system is small enough to be put in patients' rooms and can be powered by standard electrical outlets. An attached Apple iPad handles postprocessing, from which, clinically useful images may be obtained.

For the high field images (1.5 or 3T MRI) which will be used for the ground truth subcortical segmentations, high field T2 scans were obtained at the University of Cape Town, Makerere University, and Aga Khan University Hospital on, respectively, a Siemens 3T Skyra, Siemens 1.5T Sempra, and Toshiba 3T Titan scanner within days of scanning on the Hyperfine SWOOP in order to obtain low and high field matching T2 image pairs.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Low field images from Hyperfine SWOOP used at both sites

Magnetic field strength 0.064T, sequence type: spin echo, TR 1.5s, TE 5ms, TI 400ms

High field images at Makerere University

Magnetic field strength 1.5T, sequence type: spin echo, TR 5s, TE 95 ms

High field images at AKU

Magnetic field strength 3T, sequence type: spin echo, TR 3.2s, TE 352 ms

High field images at UCT

Magnetic field strength 3T, sequence type: spin echo, TR 3.2s, TE 561 ms

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Data was acquired at the (1) University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa, (2) Kawempe National Referral Hospital, Makerere University, Kampala, Uganda, and (3) Aga Khan University Hospital, Karachi, Pakistan

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

All images were collected by trained personnel with experience imaging patients at the institutions listed above. All subcortical segmentations were approved by a board certified pediatric neuroradiologist.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

One case encompasses a preprocessed low field T2 MR image and a single accompanying high field MRI -derived segmentation of the following subcortical structures with the following labels : 0 - background, 1- left hippocampus, 2 - right hippocampus, 3 - left lateral ventricle, 4 - right lateral ventricle, 5 - left caudate nuclei, 6 - right caudate nuclei, 7 - left putamen and globus pallidus, 8 - right putamen and globus pallidus, 9 - left thalamus, 10 - right thalamus, 11 - corpus callosum. These segmentations will also be manually refined on the corresponding uLF images, and the resulting uLFderived segmentations will be made available for participants to use as additional reference data.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The images in validation and testing used in the QA task that also have matched high field data will be considered for validation and testing in the segmentation task. Additional data is being acquired through the UNITY Consortium and will be added as it becomes available. .

The number of subjects in training, validation and test cohorts is as follows.

UCT, MAK, and AKU with 47, 16, and 12 training cases respectively for a total of 75 cases.

UCT, MAK, and AKU with 7, 2, and 7 validation cases respectively for a total of 16 cases.

UCT , MAK, and AKU with 7, 2, and 7 test cases respectively for a total of 16 cases.

c) How much of the data are already annotated (stratified by train test in percentage)?

100% of the training, test and validation data is annotated.

d) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The total number of cases has been determined based on the available data. We collected data from different sites to introduce diversity, thereby avoiding overfitting and achieving better generalizability for the proposed models in the tasks. To prevent overlap between scans from one subject in the training cohort and those in the validation and test cohorts (due to multiple scans from a single subject), we will consider subjects rather than individual scans during the data division for training and validation. We follow the standard division of data for training (70%), validation (15%), and test (15%) and apply it to each site to get the final division for training, validation and test cohorts.

e) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

N/A

f) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

All high field segmentations will be in NIFTI format with the following labels :0 - background, 1- left hippocampus, 2 - right hippocampus, 3 - left lateral ventricle, 4 - right lateral ventricle, 5 - left caudate nuclei, 6 - right caudate nuclei, 7 - left putamen and globus pallidus, 8 - right putamen and globus pallidus, 9 - left thalamus, 10 - right thalamus, 11 - corpus callosum

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Initial segmentation/annotation was performed manually by research assistants, and were corrected manually by an expert rater. A neuroradiologist reviewed and approved the segmentation protocol.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

An outline of the segmentation protocol is detailed below. A similar protocol is used for other structures in the task.

Hippocampus Segmentation Protocol in ITK-SNAP

1. Loading the Main Image:

Launch ITK-SNAP, and load the main MRI image containing the brain structure of interest.

2. Adjusting Image Contrast:

Navigate to the "Tools" menu.

Adjust Image contrast to optimize contrast settings for differentiating white matter and gray matter.

3. Defining Labels:

Label 1 (red): Represents the left hippocampus.

Label 2 (green): Represents the right hippocampus.

4. Main Toolbar:

Use the crosshair mode to select a voxel of interest, which will be displayed in all three planes. Adjust the zoom level as per your preference.

Utilize the paint brush mode for segmenting regions.

Using a Square Brush Shape (Size 2), maintain a consistent 2x2 voxel boundary for accurate segmentation.

6. Starting in Sagittal View:

Identify a sagittal slice that exhibits the maximum extent of the hippocampus.

Begin segmenting the gray matter while adjusting the brush opacity as needed.

Pay attention to the boundaries where the anterior and posterior sides of the hippocampus meet, especially at the ventricles.

7. Lateral Segmentation in Sagittal View:

Gradually move laterally (away from the brain center) and continue segmenting the hippocampus slice by slice. Hippocampus will gradually become smaller and thinner.

8. Medial Segmentation in Sagittal View:

After reaching the lateral boundary, move medially (toward the brain center).

Identify the "claw-shaped" structure, which may represent the ventricles.

The "thumb" of this claw determines when to split the hippocampus in the sagittal view.

Ensure a gradual split of the hippocampus without abrupt shape shifts, maintaining the integrity of the structure.

9. Segmenting the Head and Tail:

After the split, continue segmentation until the anterior head of the hippocampus disappears. The posterior tail will gradually vanish after the head disappears.

10. Coronal View Segmentation:

Begin segmentation from the posterior side in the coronal view.

Progress slice by slice towards the anterior side, identifying contrast differences as well as consistency in the shape shifting.

Employ crosshair mode more frequently in the coronal view to validate segmentation from the sagittal view.

11. Axial View Segmentation:

Start segmentation from the superior side in the axial view.

Move slice by slice towards the inferior side.

As you approach the endpoint in the axial view, ensure that the segmentation concludes before the corpus callosum joins. This serves as your reference for the boundary in the axial view.

12. Maintaining 2x2 Voxel Density:

Throughout the segmentation process, prevent holes or any 1x1 voxel stranding.

Maintaining a 2x2 voxel density is crucial for accurate boundary preservation.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The segmenters have many years of experience in assessing MR image quality. In addition, the protocols and subsets of the segmentations were verified by Dr. Marvin Nelson, a pediatric neuroradiologist with 50+ years of experience.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

N/A

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

All images were first converted to NIFTI from DICOM using dcm2nii. These low field images are defaced for full anonymization using our defacing pipeline which is available in our github repository located here -

<https://github.com/LISACHallengeOfficial/2025Preprocessing/tree/main>

Each orthogonally acquired trio of anisotropic low field T2 images are reconstructed to form a single higher resolution combined isotropic T2 image as described in [2].

These images and all background high resolution images then follow a processing pipeline of bias field correction, skullstripping and linear registration as detailed in [3].

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

We will provide intra-rater reliability scores to estimate the magnitude of human error in image annotation.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N/A

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

We will employ four metrics, Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC), Hausdorff Distance (HD), Average Symmetric Surface Distance (ASSD), and Relative Volume Error (RVE) on the respective segmentation predictions.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

Metric choice was chosen from recommendations found in [5] which presents a checklist which authors of biomedical image analysis challenges are encouraged to include in their submission when giving a paper on a challenge into review. The purpose of the checklist is to standardize and facilitate the review process and raise interpretability and reproducibility of challenge results by making relevant information explicit.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking. Ideally, provide the ranking scheme as a concrete pseudo code.

We will take the mean across their respective metrics in order to obtain rankings. Standard deviations will also be calculated and given.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Submissions that have missing results or cannot provide results because inference fails on a test case will be assigned the lowest possible score for the failed test case using metrics relevant to the task. For example, if a missing result or failed inference occurs in Task 2, values would be set to 0% for DSC, the maximum size of the image for both HD and ASSD, and 100% for relative volume error.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

Submissions that have missing results or cannot provide results because inference fails on a test case will be assigned the lowest possible score for the failed test case using metrics relevant to the task. For example, if a missing result or failed inference occurs in Task 2, values would be set to 0% for DSC, the maximum size of the

image for both HD and ASSD, and 100% for relative volume error. The ranking system described will be used to obtain a fair and complete comparison across all metrics between participants. We desire a ranking scheme that is empirical, objective, and provides both participants and organizers with a clear understanding of the 'best' challenge solution.

Statistical analyses

Provide an overview of the statistical approaches used in the scope of the challenge analysis. Details can be provided in the parameters below. For each parameter, justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used and, if necessary, add a description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions required for the particular statistical approach.

Permutational analyses will be employed to evaluate uncertainties in rankings. Each team's performance will be evaluated separately for the left and right subcortical structures (or in the single structure in the case of the corpus callosum). Rankings for the measures will be combined by averaging, and statistical significance will be assessed exclusively for segmentation performance measures. This assessment will involve permuting the relative ranks for each segmentation measure, considering left and right subcortical structure segmentation, per subject in the testing data. In addition, deeper insights into performance differences among participating models will be obtained through pairwise comparisons performed within a bootstrap framework, thereby complementing the permutation-based ranking assessment and ensuring a consistent and robust evaluation of statistical significance.

Provide a description of how the precision of the performance estimates of individual algorithms is assessed (e.g. confidence interval of the mean on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap, confidence interval of the accuracy on the test set computed using percentile bootstrap).

The precision of performance estimates for individual algorithms will be assessed using percentile bootstrap confidence intervals on the held-out test set. Test cases will be resampled with replacement while keeping the sample size fixed, and performance metrics (DSC, HD, HD95, ASSD, and RVE) will be recomputed for each bootstrap resample. In addition to reporting individual metrics, a Mean Error (ME) is calculated based on the average of 1-DSC, HD, HD95, ASSD, and RVE values. The metric values computed on the full test set will be reported as point estimates, and the 2.5th and 97.5th percentiles of the bootstrap distribution will be reported as the 95% confidence interval.

Provide a description of how variability of the performance of individual algorithms across test cases is assessed (e.g. SD across test cases, IQR, graphs, reporting outliers...).

Performance variability across test cases be assessed by reporting the standard deviation of per-case performance metrics. This will provide a descriptive measure of how algorithm performance varies across different test cases. Where appropriate, additional summary statistics or visualizations (e.g., boxplots) may be used to further illustrate performance distributions.

Provide a description of how variability of rankings is assessed.

Algorithm rankings will be based on a Mean Error (ME) (the average of values of 1-DSC, HD, HD95, ASSD and RVE). To assess ranking variability, bootstrap resampling of the test cases is performed. For each bootstrap iteration, test cases are resampled with replacement, performance metrics are recomputed, ME is calculated, and algorithms are ranked accordingly. This results in a distribution of ranks for each algorithm across bootstrap iterations. Ranking stability is assessed using the median rank and interquartile range derived from this

distribution.

Provide a description of statistical tests that are used to assess whether the differences in performance between algorithms are statistically significant.

As bootstrap analysis is used to address the questions above, statistical differences between algorithms can also be assessed within the same bootstrap framework. For each pair of algorithms, the difference in ME is calculated across bootstrap resamples, yielding a distribution of score differences. A 95% percentile confidence interval (CI) for this difference is derived from the distribution. A performance difference is considered statistically significant if the corresponding confidence interval does not include zero. To account for multiple pairwise comparisons across all participating teams, p-values derived from the bootstrap distributions are adjusted using the Holm–Bonferroni procedure with a significance level of $\alpha=0.05$.

Provide a description of the missing data handling.

All test cases are required to be present for all participating teams. If a team fails to produce a result for a case, that case will be treated as missing for that team and will be assigned the worst possible score for that metric for ranking purposes. This avoids inflating performance estimates and ensures comparability across participants. No subject-level data will be removed from evaluation.

Indicate any software product that is used for all data analysis methods.

Python (NumPy, SciPy, Pandas) and Synapse platform (for data hosting, submission management, and automated evaluation)

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

[1] Bottani S, Burgos N, Maire A, Wild A, Ströer S, Dormont D, Colliot O; APPRIMAGE Study Group. Automatic quality control of brain T1-weighted magnetic resonance images for a clinical data warehouse. *Med Image Anal.* 2022 Jan;75:102219. doi: 10.1016/j.media.2021.102219. Epub 2021 Sep 3. PMID: 34773767.

[2] Deoni, S. C., O'Muircheartaigh, J., Ljungberg, E., Huentelman, M., & Williams, S. C. (2022). Simultaneous high-resolution T2-weighted imaging and quantitative T2 mapping at low magnetic field strengths using a multiple TE and multi-orientation acquisition approach. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*, 88(3), 1273-1281

[3] Rouhi, R., Tanedo, J., Wei, I.M., Valder, M., Zanzal, S., Gajawelli, N., ... & Lepore, N. (2023, November). Automated Segmentation of the Hippocampus in Pediatric Imaging. In 2023 19th International Symposium on Medical

Information Processing and Analysis (SIPAIM) (pp. 1-5), IEEE.

[4] Ravi D; Alzheimer's Disease Neuroimaging Initiative; Barkhof F, Alexander DC, Puglisi L, Parker GJM, Eshaghi A. An efficient semi-supervised quality control system trained using physics-based MRI-artefact generators and adversarial training. *Med Image Anal.* 2024 Jan;91:103033. doi 10.1016/j.media.2023.103033 Epub 2023 Nov 20. PMID 38000256

[5] Lena Maier-Hein, Annika Reinke, Michal Kozubek, Anne L. Martel, Tal Arbel, Matthias Eisenmann, Allan Hanbury, Pierre Jannin, Henning Müller, Sinan Onogur, Julio Saez-Rodriguez, Bram van Ginneken, Annette Kopp-Schneider, Bennett A. Landman, BIAS: Transparent reporting of biomedical image analysis challenges, *Medical Image Analysis*, Volume 66, 2020, 101796, ISSN 1361-8415, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.media.2020.101796>.

Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

N/A